
Characterization of wind turbine siting parameters in complex terrain using remote sensing

A Data Management Plan created using DMPOnline

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Project abstract:

Current wind turbines can reach more than 120 m of hub height and five acres of swept area, hence inhibiting the exclusive usage of tall met masts. Additionally, when considering complex terrains, the wind resource characterization has to account for flow distortion effects, which are highly site dependent. In order to achieve a detailed wind resource mapping, accurate local data has to be available to calibrate current resource assessment methodologies. The present-day solution of commercial Doppler laser remote sensing technology, called wind lidars, has to rely on the necessity to average the wind over a large volume, which presume a flat terrain with a horizontally homogeneous flow. For this reason, the current IEC standard considers remote sensing application for flat terrain, allowing only traditional anemometry on complex sites. The Windscanner system aims to overcome such limitations with the usage of two or more synchronized intersecting lasers aiming at the same point. Meso and micro scale model validation for resource assessment using Windscanner technology is a topic to be better explored, where a measurement campaign with high data recovery rate is expected.

The present project aims to select an site with highly complex terrain with particular meteorological features to address the following research questions:

- Which large and micro scale flow patterns are truly relevant for wind turbine siting in highly complex terrain?
- How to reduce the uncertainty of wind turbine siting using multi-lidar measurements?
- How to couple in-situ measurements with a numerical model chain (meso to microscale) for wind resource assessment?

The project will design and conduct a full-scale measurement campaign using the Windscanner technology to provide a valuable dataset for numerical model validation and for insights into atmospheric physics. This document aims to underline the data management plan, which will follow the most recent and best practices from data collection to dissemination.

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Data Collection

Describe the data that will be collected.

The Alaiz experiment (ALEX17) was performed at Alaiz, located in Navarre region (Spain), a site consisting of a mountain range of 1000m above sea level (a.s.l.). To the North, along the prevailing wind direction, measurement equipment are located at a valley 500m lower in altitude bounded by a 750 m asl. hill located 6 km north of Alaiz.

The experimental layout aims to provide a high-quality database to explore wind flow phenomena and derive validation datasets of high-resolution mesoscale-to-microscale models with strong coupling between terrain and thermal stratification.

This full-scale experiment is a joint effort between research groups of Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Renewable Energy Centre of Spain (CENER) and University of Balearic Islands (UIB).

The dataset to be collected consists of raw as well as processed data of multiple meteorological instruments distributed the experimental domain. Since the dataset is heterogeneous and with multiple sensors, it's useful to define a Data Collection, which will be composed by nine distinct datasets, namely:

1. Multi-lidar dataset: 5 x Long-range WindScanner (LRWS) systems
2. Surface fluxes dataset: 9 x Surface Layer Stations (SLS)
3. WLS70 dataset: 1 x Windcube 70 (WLS70) lidar profiler
4. Alaiz Test Site dataset: 1 x 118m flux-profile meteorological mast (called MP5)
5. SEB and RASS dataset: 1 x Surface Energy Budget Station (SEB) and 1 x WindRASS sodar system
6. Navarre meteo stations dataset: 22 x surface climatological stations from Meteo Navarra
7. Flux-profile dataset: 4 x 80m met masts equipped with 3D sonic anemometers
8. Complementary measurements dataset: 2 x 80m met masts with cup anemometers along with 6x80m temperature and relative humidity profiles.
9. Landscape dataset: Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with 2x2m resolution as well as derived roughness length with 10x10m resolution.

Apart from the experimental data, other important documents will be included in the dataset as they planned to be properly stored and FAIR, such as:

- Experiment Logbook (Mattermost)
- Photos
- Calibration certificates
- Georeferenced position of all sensors (Leica campaign)

Describe any restrictions to the data.

The ALEX17 experiment is planned to be concluded within the context of an EU funded project called New European Wind Atlas ([NEWA](#)), grant number ERANET+ - ENER/FP7/618122/NEWA, hence all the experimental data collected will be publicly available under **CC BY 4.0** license.

Data Storage

Describe the IT infrastructure to be used.

During the data collection period all data is stored locally in each measurement equipment and a 3G network will be used to, in real time, sync the collected data with a local server.

The real time data storage plays a double roll of security in the collection by redundancy but also in the monitoring of the experiment, in order to make sure that all instruments are running and the collected data meets the scientific planning objectives. To accomplish real time data sync an batch script runs in all sensors as a schedule task responsible to send daily data packages to the server.

In the backend, the server is planned to be organized according with the defined Data Collection. The preliminary directory tree can be seen below:

```
|-- data
|   |-- CENER_Masts
|   |-- DTU_Masts
|   |-- DTU_WindScanner
```

```
| |-- DTU_WLS70_Profiler
| |-- METEO_Navarra
| |-- UIB_SEB
| |-- UIB_SLS
| `-- UIB_WR
|-- docs
| |-- Leica_campaign
| `-- Logbook
|-- landscape
`-- photos
    |-- 00.Risoe_Pre_Campaign
    |-- 01.Comissioning
    |-- 02.Site
    |-- 03.Windscanners
    |-- 04.Masts
    |-- 05.WLS70
    |-- 06.Team
    |-- 07.Decommissioning
    |-- 08.SLS_stations
    |-- 09.WRASS_SEB
    `-- 10.ALEX17_selected_pics
```

The server is also mirrored in two distinct drives as a backup.

Documentation

Describe the metadata to be associated with the data.

Most of the experimental data is planned to be stored in the standard [NetCDF4](#) format, which is able to have embedded metadata and be, to some extent, self-describing. Moreover, a major part of the collected is meteorological, allowing to apply existing and well accepted metadata such as the [CF convention](#).

For the specific and innovative wind lidar data recently developed metadata conventions will be applied, including the usage of [tools](#) to also convert this type of data into standard formats.

For publishing data description, i.e. metadata cards, the [wind energy taxonomies and restricted vocabularies](#) will be applied. [DTU data](#) platform, which has the taxonomies implemented, will be used for this tasks.

Describe the types of documentation that will accompany the data.

The experiment documentation aims to cover details not possible to be reported within the metadata. This includes the scientific objectives of the experiment, layout of the measurement sensor, calibration/positioning procedures, as well as data quality and availability. These and other details are aimed to be covered in the Experimentla Campaign & Data Report, that will be published in [Zenodo](#) and also point to the access for the Data Collection which will be reported on DTU data (data publishing platform of the Technical University of Denmark).

Data Sharing

Describe which data will be shared.

All experimental data, metadata and supportive documentation of the experiment will be publicly available. These means that all raw and processed data from each instrument will be stored following the directory tree from this plan.

Since standard formats (e.g. netCDF4) planned to be used, visualization and preliminary data analysis tools are already available from the scientific community, such as [Panoply](#) and other packages. The higher level data analysis will be able to be reproduced with shared code published in [GitHub](#).

Describe how the data will be shared for possible reuse.

The nine datasets described in the Data Collection section will be published in the [DTU Data](#) repository, so each dataset can have its specific metadata description and an access link to the storage server. Furthermore, the division of data sets is a way to properly acknowledge the main responsible (first author) of each part of the experiment, since it's a collaborative effort between three institutions: [DTU Wind Energy](#), [CENER](#) and [UIB](#).

Since the most of the datasets have a large size (>100 GB), hence greater than the repository storage limit, the data will be available through an [OpenDAP](#) protocol. This tool allows the selection of parts of the dataset to be downloaded, such as a specific period in time, reducing the amount of data and making the dataset more intuitive and reusable. As a Plan B, a sftp link will also be in place to directly download all the raw data.

Results from the formal analysis will be shared as journal papers and reference back to the repository and experimental report.

Long-term Preservation

Describe how data will be archived beyond the scope of the research project.

With experience of previous experiments it's possible to make a fairly accurate estimation on storage requirements for the complete data collection of the ALEX17, see below:

```
|-- data, TOTAL: 2637.4 GB
| |-- CENER_Masts, 1200 GB
| |-- DTU_Masts, 385 GB
| |-- DTU_WindScanner, 1000 GB
| |-- DTU_WLS70_Profiler, 11 GB
| |-- METEO_Navarra, 0.70 GB
| |-- UIB_SEB, 22 GB
| |-- UIB_SLS, 0.70 GB
| `-- UIB_WR, 18 GB
```

Therefore, in order to store the raw data of the entire experiment, including a safety margin, it will be required around 3TB of disk space. The local DTU Wind Energy server can easily host this amount of data for a long term with a backup for redundancy, hence the long-term preservation of the entire dataset is feasible.